

Finite-Time and Infinite-Time Horizon State-Dependent Riccati Equation for Swinging-up and Control of a Rotary Drone Pendulum

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Abstract—The control, prototyping, and experimentation of rotor-based systems (aerial robotic platforms) were highlighted recently for rotation around pipes for inspection, measurement, and maintenance. The application of the rotary inspection comes from chemical plants and, the oil and gas industry where in some cases, access to all perimeters of the pipes is difficult. Rotary aerial systems then are good candidates. Here in this work, a novel system is proposed for rotary inspection based on a two-link rotary drone pendulum. The modeling of the system released highly nonlinear dynamics. Finite-time and infinite-time horizon state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE) are chosen to control the system, both in the domain of nonlinear optimal control. These nonlinear controllers are suitable for handling the dynamics and the finite horizon design offers a rapid response for swinging up and stabilization around the pipe. Solving this challenge in control enables us to move forward with the design and implementation of the system on a real setup and prototype. The Simulation and comparison of finite-time (state-dependent differential Riccati equation (SDDRE)) and infinite-time SDRE were done; it showed successful regulation with faster response and less error for the finite-time method.

Keywords: Rotary Pendulum; SDRE; SDDRE; Finite-time; Drone; Aerial robotics, UAVs.

I. INTRODUCTION

The control challenge of rotor-based actuation rotary inverted pendulums has been investigated several times recently [1]–[7]. The flying platform is subjected to more disturbance and uncertainty rather than conventional inverted pendulums such as rotary [8], [9], on cart [10], [11], etc. The control design for the drone pendulum includes two parts: controlling the drone itself and also a control algorithm for the stabilization of the inverted pendulum. Barawkar et al. designed a flying inverted pendulum using a linear quadratic regulator (LQR) controller for a system with unknown length [6]. Lu et al. used the LQR controller for rotor-based inverted pendulum (RBIP) and tuning with particle swarm optimization [5]. Chen et al. used a genetic algorithm to design an optimal control for a flying pendulum [4]. The flight paths were selected as circular and eight-shaped curves to show the stability of the pendulum in the flights. Transportation of load with hanging pendulum structures below the drones was also proposed. Estevez et al. used

a drone and pendulum control for stabilization of the load [2]. A hybrid rotor-based pendulum on a wheeled platform was modeled and controlled with experimentation [7]. Fan et al. used a pendulum-plucked rotor for ultra-low frequency control [3]. Stabilizing pendulum systems is a challenging task in control design; therefore, this design and case study is a way to check the performance of the controllers for rotary mechatronic systems.

Chemical plants, and oil and gas refineries have pipes as an important part of the plants for transferring the material, fluid/gas. The corrosion, thickness of the pipes, and cover of them must be checked regularly. Robotics offers an automatic method for inspection and maintenance (IM) of the systems [12], [13]. While pipes could be inspected and monitored with robotic systems from inside [14]–[18], the focus of this work is the IM robotic systems for operation from outside of the pipe. For IM of the pipelines from outside, a measurement device is needed such as an ultrasonic sensor, electromagnetic acoustic transducers, piezoelectric transducer, etc. [19]. These measurement components must be installed on the robotic platforms for carrying out the inspection. The idea of a crawling robot was proposed as a worm-like robot in 1987 for using an ultrasonic sensor [20]. Fukuda et al. proposed two connected grippers for grasping a pipe and a linear motor for forward motion [20]. The gripper's special design and rotary motion allowed moving over the flanges in a pipeline with junctions.

HYFLIERS was a project to address the inspection of a rack of pipes and a single pipe in oil and gas refineries [21]–[23]. It was dedicated comprehensively to the inspection and maintenance of pipes using different sensors and customized add-ons, mounted on multi-rotor drones. Due to the security of the refineries, most of the add-ons could be released on the pipeline and the drone could fly back to the ground station and wait for the inspection unit to complete the task. Cacace et al. presented a hybrid aerial-ground robotic system for thickness measurement of pipes using ultrasonic sensors and multi-rotor carrier [21]. The specific design of the manipulator allowed inspection of the elbows as well. The rotary measurement component of the manipulator performed the inspection for the parts under the pipes while the drone stayed in the landing position [22]. Yu and Lippiello studied the mathematical equations and control problem of the 6D pose task of end-effector for trajectory tracking [23]. Landing on pipes in chemical plants and refineries was discussed and a soft-landing method was investigated to reduce the hard contact between the drone and pipes in inspection missions [24], [25]. “Safe Inspection

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and Maintenance supporting workers with modular robots, Artificial intelligence, and augmented Reality¹ (SIMAR) is an EU project dealing with intelligent and safe inspection in plants and refineries. The project follows the results of the HYFLIERS and adds more safety and intelligence in the interaction with humans and the use of augmented reality. This work proposes an initiative idea on a drone mechanism for rotary inspection of the pipes within the framework of the SIMAR project.

Rotary inspection of pipes using a drone (or rotor-based mechanisms) and robotic mechanisms were investigated in the literature [26]–[28]. The preliminary ideas of inspection of pipes from the outer side using a drone suggested installation of the inspection device on the drone and the multi-rotor system moved around the pipe to give access to the inspection device [28], [29]. Lopez-Lora et al. presented a hybrid drone for pipe inspection [30]. The robot was compatible with two add-ons for pipe inspection, one of them grasping a single pipe and rolling along it and the other one moving on a rack of pipes. The crawling robot provided enough force to stay on the pipe while doing the inspection. Nekoo et al. designed a benchmark for rotary inspection around pipes using a state-dependent Riccati equation (SDRE) controller and iterative learning [31].

The SDRE controller is a popular method for controlling the pendulum mechanism (on a cart, rotary inverted pendulum, double link, etc.) since the nonlinear optimal gain of the control law proposes an input in which all the state variables interact in stabilization. The argument holds for RBIP for simulation and experiments [27], [31]. The cost function of the optimal control sets a trade-off between the errors and inputs. The method has been widely used in nonlinear systems such as robotic arms, underwater vehicle control, aerospace applications, space robotics, etc. Optimality along with the nonlinear structure of the controller is one of the most important advantages of the SDRE. Considering the finite horizon in the optimal cost function, the controller changes to finite-time SDRE. The finite-time SDRE solves a differential equation with final boundary condition to penalize the states at final time [32]. This work compares both SDRE and finite-time one to see the effect of rapid convergence on the performance of the system.

The dynamical system in this work is a rotor-based pendulum for swinging up and stabilizing around a pipe. The drone is attached to a rotating ring with a double-link mechanism. This mechanism adds additional degrees of freedom for the drone to move easier and relax constraints in pure rotation. The previous versions of the rotor-based pendulum included pure rotary motion and variable pitch rotors to provide negative thrust [27], [31], which motivated this work to add a double link mechanism.

The contributions of this work are 1) to propose a novel double-link rotor-based inverted pendulum for swinging up and stabilization around pipes, and 2) and implement finite and infinite-time horizon SDRE optimal control on the

Fig. 1. The rotor-based double-link inverted pendulum schematic for stabilization around pipes.

double-link rotor-based pendulum.

Section II presents the modeling of the proposed double-link rotor-based pendulum. The SDRE controller in finite and infinite time design and the solution to the differential Riccati equation are stated in Section III. Simulation and results are reported in Section IV. The summary and conclusions are stated in Section V.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODELING

The pure rotation of a rotor-based pendulum, one-DoF, model puts a constraint on the setup and urges the designer to use compensation mechanisms such as variable-pitch propellers to provide negative thrust for swinging up and stabilization easier [31]. The two-DoF version in radial motion still kept the pure rotation constraint since it did not allow the drone to change the direction of the thrust vector [27]. In this work, an additional DoF is added to the design to relax the pure rotation constraint on the system and this leads to the possibility of using conventional propellers (one-directional thrust). Then the difference between the amplitude of the thrust forces provides the necessary torque for swinging up. The schematic of the system and configuration of the double-link pendulum drone are illustrated in Fig. 1.

The inertial base of the system is denoted by $O = \{i_0, j_0\}$ axis, rotary clamp base is shown by $C = \{i_c, j_c\}$, and the base of the drone is defined by $A = \{i_a, j_a\}$. The global frame is set at point O , and the first and second DoF of the system are presented by C and A . The generalized coordinates of the system are

$$\mathbf{q}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha(t) \\ \phi(t) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\alpha(t)$ (rad) is the angle of the rotating ring around the center of the pipe with respect to vertical axis j_0 , and $\phi(t)$ (rad) is the angle of the rotating drone around point A with respect to vertical axis j_a . The input thrusts of the left and right propellers are $u_1(t)$ (N) and $u_2(t)$ (N), and the gravity applies to the system in the direction of $-j_0$. The velocity of generalized coordinates (1) are defined by

$$\dot{\mathbf{q}}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\alpha}(t) \\ \dot{\phi}(t) \end{bmatrix}. \quad (2)$$

¹<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101070604>

The equation of motion of the RBIP is presented as:

$$\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q}(t))\ddot{\mathbf{q}}(t) + \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{q}(t), \dot{\mathbf{q}}(t)) + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{q}(t)) = \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{q}(t))\mathbf{u}(t), \quad (3)$$

where the inertia matrix is $\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$, the generated terms by gravity acceleration are collected in $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{q}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$, Coriolis and centrifugal terms are arranged in the vector $\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{q}(t), \dot{\mathbf{q}}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^2 \times \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2$, and the transformation of the thrust inputs from body of the drone to generalized coordinates are done by the matrix $\mathbf{U}(\mathbf{q}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 2}$; more specifically:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q}(t)) &= \begin{bmatrix} I_{c,zz} + m_a r_c^2 + m_c (h_c - r_c)^2 & h_a m_a r_c \cos(\alpha(t) - \phi(t)) \\ h_a m_a r_c \cos(\alpha(t) - \phi(t)) & I_{a,zz} + h_a^2 m_a \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{q}(t), \dot{\mathbf{q}}(t)) &= \begin{bmatrix} -h_a m_a r_c \sin(\alpha(t) - \phi(t)) \dot{\phi}^2(t) \\ h_a m_a r_c \sin(\alpha(t) - \phi(t)) \dot{\alpha}^2(t) \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{q}(t)) &= \begin{bmatrix} g(-h_c m_c + m_a r_c + m_c r_c) \sin \alpha(t) \\ g h_a m_a \sin \alpha(t) \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{U}(\mathbf{q}(t)) &= \begin{bmatrix} -r_c \sin(\alpha(t) - \phi(t)) & -r_c \sin(\alpha(t) - \phi(t)) \\ -b & b \end{bmatrix}, \end{aligned}$$

in which $I_{c,zz}, I_{a,zz}(\text{kgm}^2)$ are the moment of inertia of the clamp and the aerial platform, respectively, $m_c, m_a(\text{kg})$ are the mass of them, $g(\text{m/s}^2)$ is the gravity constant, $b(\text{m})$ is the distance between motor and center-of-mass (CoM) of the quadrotor, $r_c(\text{m})$ is the distance between the center of the pipe and the rotary joint of the clamp, $h_c(\text{m})$ is the distance between the joint of the clamp and CoM of the clamp, and $h_a(\text{m})$ is the distance between the joint and CoM of the aerial platform.

Considering the generalized coordinate vector (1) and its velocity (2) as the state variable of the double-link inverted pendulum, the state vector is introduced

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{q}(t) \\ \dot{\mathbf{q}}(t) \end{bmatrix},$$

which generates the state-space representation of the system using the dynamics in Eq. (3):

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 2} & \mathbf{I}_{2 \times 2} \\ -\mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{q}(t))\mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q}(t)) & -\mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{q}(t))\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}(t), \dot{\mathbf{q}}(t)) \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}(t) + \\ & \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{0}_{2 \times 2} \\ \mathbf{M}^{-1}(\mathbf{q}(t))\mathbf{U}(\mathbf{q}(t)) \end{bmatrix} \mathbf{u}(t), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}(t) &= \begin{bmatrix} u_1(t) \\ u_2(t) \end{bmatrix}, \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{q}(t)) = \begin{bmatrix} G_{1,1}(\mathbf{q}(t)) & 0 \\ G_{2,1}(\mathbf{q}(t)) & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \\ \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}(t), \dot{\mathbf{q}}(t)) &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & C_{1,2}(\mathbf{q}(t)) \\ C_{2,1}(\mathbf{q}(t)) & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$G_{1,1}(\mathbf{q}(t)) = g(-h_c m_c + m_a r_c + m_c r_c) \left[1 - \frac{\alpha^2(t)}{6} + \frac{\alpha^4(t)}{120} - \frac{\alpha^6(t)}{5040} + \dots \right],$$

$$\begin{aligned} G_{2,1}(\mathbf{q}(t)) &= g h_a m_a \left[1 - \frac{\alpha^2(t)}{6} + \frac{\alpha^4(t)}{120} - \frac{\alpha^6(t)}{5040} + \dots \right], \\ C_{1,2}(\mathbf{q}(t)) &= -h_a m_a r_c \sin(\alpha(t) - \phi(t)) \dot{\phi}(t), \\ C_{2,1}(\mathbf{q}(t)) &= h_a m_a r_c \sin(\alpha(t) - \phi(t)) \dot{\alpha}(t). \end{aligned}$$

The state-space representation (4) is the mathematical model of the rotor-based inverted pendulum for the control design and simulation, presented in Section III and IV. $G_{1,1}(\mathbf{q}(t))$ and $G_{2,1}(\mathbf{q}(t))$ includes Taylor series expansion terms of $\sin \alpha(t)$ to facilitate the factorization process.

III. SDRE CONTROLLER

A. Infinite-Horizon

Consider the system

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{u}(t), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ and $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times m}$ are state-dependent coefficient (SDC) parameterization of the system

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)), \quad (6)$$

in which $\mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}(t), \mathbf{u}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ and $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ are vector-valued functions, smooth and continuous. The state variables are set in vector $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and the inputs in vector $\mathbf{u}(t) \in \mathbb{R}^m$.

The cost function of optimal control is [33]:

$$J(\cdot) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty [\mathbf{u}^\top(t) \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{x}^\top(t) \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{x}(t)] dt, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{m \times m}$ and $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ are weighting matrices for inputs and states; both matrices are symmetric positive, $\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ is definite and $\mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ is semi-definite.

The SDC parameterization for the pairs of $\{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)), \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))\}$ and $\{\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)), \mathbf{Q}^{1/2}(\mathbf{x}(t))\}$ in (5) and (7), must present completely controllable and observable parameterization of system (6); discussions of controllability and observability and the how to check those conditions could be visited in Ref. [34], [35].

The control law of the SDRE is

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = -\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{x}(t), \quad (8)$$

and the governing equation to find the solution to the optimal control is

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{A}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \\ & \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \\ & \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{0}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

The solution to SDRE (9) is symmetric and positive definite solution $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t)) : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ which is substituted in the control law (8) and builds the overall gain $\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ and presents the final control law:

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = -\mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}(t))\mathbf{x}(t).$$

This representation of the infinite-time horizon SDRE results in a sub-optimal control design for nonlinear systems without putting any constraint on the time of the simulation. After the transient response, the system reaches the steady-state condition and stays without change while $t \rightarrow \infty$.

B. Finite-Horizon

In order to penalize the states in a predefined final time, the structure of the controller must be transformed to finite-horizon optimal control. Therefore, the possibility of the regulation to final condition faster than infinite-horizon case will be available. The first step to change the structure is to replace the upper bound of integral in (7) with a finite value t_f (s) [33]:

$$J(\cdot) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{x}^\top(t_f) \mathbf{F} \mathbf{x}(t_f) + \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{t_f} [\mathbf{u}^\top(t) \mathbf{R}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{u}(t) + \mathbf{x}^\top(t) \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{x}(t)] dt, \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$ is the weighting matrix of states at the final time, symmetric positive semi-definite. The finite time upper bound of the integral will keep $\dot{\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ in the derivation of the SDRE, specifically, applying the optimality condition on Hamiltonian function and generates the state-dependent differential Riccati equation (SDDRE):

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{A}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \\ & \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \\ & \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = -\dot{\mathbf{P}}(\mathbf{x}(t)), \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where the boundary of the differential equation is a final condition $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t_f)) = \mathbf{F}$ which imposes a backward solution from final to initial condition [36]. There are several methods to solve this matrix differential equation (11) such as backward integration (BI), state transition matrix (STM) approach, and Lyapunov-based method [36]. The BI offers a two-round solution, the first round from the final to initial condition to solve the SDDRE and generate the solution for $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t))$, and then using the gain in a forward solution loop to complete the regulation task. The STM offers a one-round solution though it is sensitive to numerical computations and tuning that is complex. The Lyapunov-based method possesses a one-round solution option and is computationally reliable for simulations. Here in this work, the Lyapunov-based approach is used for solving the finite horizon optimal control.

C. Solution to Differential Riccati Equation

The solution to differential Riccati equation (11) requires the computation of the symmetric negative definite solution to SDRE, as in the following [37]:

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{P}_{ss}^-(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{A}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{P}_{ss}^-(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \\ & \mathbf{P}_{ss}^-(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{P}_{ss}^-(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \\ & \mathbf{Q}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{0}. \end{aligned}$$

The next step is to define a closed-loop matrix:

$$\mathbf{A}_{cl}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{P}_{ss}^-(\mathbf{x}(t)),$$

and to solve state-dependent differential Lyapunov equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = & \mathbf{A}_{cl}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{A}_{cl}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) - \\ & \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)), \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 2. The generalized coordinates of the system, angles of the ring, and the drone.

Fig. 3. The velocity states in regulation.

with final boundary condition $\mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}(t_f)) = \{\mathbf{F} - \mathbf{K}_{ss}^-(\mathbf{x}(t_f))\}^{-1}$. The solution to (12) is found by solving algebraic Lyapunov equation:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{A}_{cl}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{A}_{cl}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \\ \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{R}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t)) \mathbf{B}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t)), \end{aligned}$$

and substituting $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}(t))$ into the closed-form solution:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{X}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = & \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \exp\{\mathbf{A}_{cl}(\mathbf{x}(t))(t - t_f)\} [\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t_f)) - \\ & \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}(t))] \exp\{\mathbf{A}_{cl}^\top(\mathbf{x}(t))(t - t_f)\}, \end{aligned}$$

that generates the final answer, a symmetric positive-definite solution to the SDDRE (11) $\mathbf{P}(\mathbf{x}(t)) = \mathbf{P}_{ss}^-(\mathbf{x}(t)) + \mathbf{X}^{-1}(\mathbf{x}(t))$.

IV. SIMULATION AND RESULTS

A. Infinite-Horizon SDRE

The model for the simulation is a drone mounted on a rotary ring around a pipe with a double-link pendulum structure. The radius of the wheels of the ring is $r_w = 0.04$ (m) (four wheels around the pipe installed on a ring), the radius of the pipe for inspection is $r_{pipe} = 0.2$ (m), the distance between the center of the pipe and the first joint is $r_c = 0.39$ (m), $h_c = 0.15$ (m), the distance between the joint and CoM of the aerial platform $h_a = 0.117$ (m), mass of the drone including the motors, frame, electronics and the payload is $m_a = 3.74$ (kg), mass of the clamp is $m_c = 3.164$ (kg), the inertia of the drone and the clamp are $I_{a,zz} = 0.094$ (kgm²) and $I_{c,zz} = 0.060$ (kgm²), respectively, the gravity constant is $g = 9.81$ (m/s²), $b = 0.29$ (m), and the radius of the propeller is 0.135(m). The maximum thrust of each propeller is limited by $T_{max} = 51.4$ (N). To show the effectiveness of the design and the controller, the worst-case scenario of the initial condition is chosen for simulation which is swinging up and stabilizing on the unstable

Fig. 4. The input thrust signals of the system, “1” and “2” show the inputs for the first and the second actuator.

Fig. 5. The trajectory and configuration of the rotor-based inverted pendulum. Initial configuration of the drone: facing down under the pipe.

equilibrium point of the system. Hence, the initial condition of the system is $\mathbf{q}(0) = [\pi, \pi]^T$ (rad) with zero initial speed $\dot{\mathbf{q}}(0) = [0, 0]^T$ (rad/s). The objective is to regulate the system towards the point $\mathbf{q}(t_f) = [0, 0]^T$ (rad) with zero velocity at the final condition. The simulation time in the infinite horizon case is set to $t_f = 4$ (s).

The control weighting matrices of the inputs and states are chosen as $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{I}_{2 \times 2}$ and $\mathbf{Q} = 100 \times \text{diag}(1, 1, 3, 0.2)$. Figure 2 shows the singular motion of the inverted pendulum moving from the initial condition to the equilibrium point in 4 seconds. The angular velocities of the generalized coordinates are presented in Fig. 3. The input thrusts of the inverted pendulum are shown in Fig. 4, and finally, the configuration and trajectory of the system are plotted in Fig. 5. The system performed the flight with overshoot and regulated back to the final condition and the error in the swinging up and stabilization at the end of the final time was obtained at 0.0051 (rad).

B. Finite-Horizon SDRE

The motivation to use finite time SDRE is to speed up the regulation and reduction of the error at the final time of the operation. This option is feasible through the penalization of states at the final boundary condition and weighting matrix \mathbf{F} . Consider the same parameters of the simulation and tuning gains with only an addition of the final weighting matrix: $\mathbf{F} = 10^4 \times \mathbf{Q}$.

Considering this penalization, the time of simulation was reduced to half, 2 seconds and the results were found successful in comparison with the infinite horizon case

Fig. 6. The angles of the joint and the drone in finite time simulation.

Fig. 7. The velocity states in regulation for finite time SDRE controller.

study. The angles and angular velocities of the joint and drone are illustrated in Figs. 6 and 7. The input signals are shown in Fig. 8 which show a jump near the end of the simulation which provides a quicker response with respect to conventional SDRE. The trajectory of the system is presented in Fig. 9. Despite the reduction of the time of simulation 50%, the error reduced to 0.0019 (rad) which showed 62.7% improvement in precision. The finite time controller also reduced the overshoot significantly which is necessary for a secure motion.

C. Robustness Testing

To demonstrate the robustness of the proposed controllers, it is assumed that the aerial robotic platform is subjected to wind disturbances which can be projected along with the negative direction of $\{i_a, j_a\}$. This wind disturbance is modeled as [38], [39]: $\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{K}_{\text{dis}} \mathbf{V}_{\text{air}}$, where \mathbf{D} is aerodynamic friction and $\mathbf{K}_{\text{dis}} = \text{diag}(10^{-1}, 10^{-1})$ (Ns) is diagonal aerodynamic matrix. The matrix \mathbf{D} is added to state-space equation (4) in the lower set of the system with a negative sign similar to Coriolis or gravity terms. \mathbf{V}_{air} is the translation air velocity with $\mathbf{V}_{\text{air}} = [3.5, 1.5]^T$ (m/s). Figures 10-11 show the performance of infinite time SDRE controller under wind disturbances. Besides Figs. 12-13 demonstrate the performance of finite time SDRE controller under the wind disturbances. These figures verify that the proposed two SDRE controllers hold robustness properties for some disturbances.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work presented a comparative study on swinging up and stabilizing a rotor-based inverted pendulum with a double linkage mechanism. The constrained rotation around pipes has been the subject of research for inspection of pipes

Fig. 8. The input thrust signals of the system in finite time case, “1” and “2” show the inputs for the first and the second actuator.

Fig. 9. The trajectory and configuration of the rotor-based inverted pendulum in the simulation of finite horizon section. Initial configuration of the drone: facing down under the pipe.

in refineries and oil and gas plants. The critical part of the stabilization is solving the control problem which requires negative thrust for pure rotations. In this work, a novel double-link pendulum was proposed and implemented using the SDRE controller. Both infinite and finite time versions of the optimal control law were applied to the proposed dynamics and compared. The finite time controller could reduce the time of the regulation by 50% while reducing the error by 62.7%. This work clarified the effectiveness of the proposed design for rotary inspection prototypes and provided some estimations on future experimental prototypes.

Future study. Generalizing the dynamics and control implementation for a 3D case. Prototyping the system for real experiments on a pipe to perform the inspection around that.

Fig. 10. The generalized coordinates of the system, angles of the ring, and the drone of infinite time SDRE controller under the wind disturbance.

Fig. 11. The input thrust signals of the system of infinite time SDRE controller under the wind disturbance, “1” and “2” show the inputs for the first and the second actuator.

Fig. 12. The generalized coordinates of the system, angles of the ring, and the drone of finite time SDRE controller under the wind disturbance.

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Fig. 13. The input thrust signals of the system of finite time SDRE controller under the wind disturbance.

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